

EdTech Hub

Clear evidence, better decisions, more learning.

The global stakes of digitalization in education

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EdTech Hub is a global non-profit research partnership.

Our goal is to **empower people by giving them the evidence they need** to make decisions about technology in education.

Why we're here

Technology has the potential to help solve the global learning crisis. But that potential is **not being realised**.

Why hasn't EdTech realised its potential?

- There isn't great evidence about what is most and least effective
- Key issues are under-researched
- Evidence is hard to find, hard to access, and hard to use
- Which makes it hard to make good policy decisions and hard to design effective interventions
- Stakeholders are disconnected from researchers and from one another

The Hub aims to address these obstacles

The Hub offering

7 tools and approaches for generating evidence

1. Large commissioned research studies

Global PIs, feed into smart buys body of evidence (fully external)

3. Hub-led desk-based studies

Evidence reviews, methods and guidance

5. Real world, EdTech Sandboxes

Designed to fast track EdTech that addresses the needs of focus countries. Provides pioneers with access to tools, evidence, and implementation support to unlock scale.

6. Technical assistance

Collaborative support in planning and execution alongside decision makers

2. Hub-led in-country research studies

In-country, led by Hub-PIs, range of methods and sizes

4. Rapid commissions and calls

Target priority high potential evidence gaps and explore new work (e.g. C-19 call)

7. Helpdesk service

Just-in-time evidence-based advice and resources for decision makers

These form the Hub's integrated offering for effective evidence generation - all underpinned by **communication and dissemination** for uptake with decision makers in and out of government.

Building Back Better (BBB) in the COVID context

Emergency remediation and returning to “business as usual” will have minimal impact on learning targets. Other initiatives are needed to meet the learning needs of students.

Source: Authors' calculations using data from World Bank, 2019.

Source: [World Bank, 2020](#)

<https://globaldatalab.org/shdi/maps/shdi/>

Attaining curriculum reform

Significant misalignment often arises between:

Attaining EdTech reform

Significant misalignment often arises between:

Intended EdTech reform
(i.e., what the official guidance says)

Attained student learning reform
(i.e., what students actually learn)

Implemented EdTech reform
(i.e., what teachers and learners actually do)

Factors for [EdTech] implementation success

**1. Curriculum
focus**

2. Assessments

**3. Teacher
professional
development**

**4. Learning &
teaching
resources**

**5. System
capacity**

**6. Financial
resources**

**7. Language of
instruction**

**8. School
leadership**

Linking curriculum reform and BBB

As schools prepare to reopen, curriculum reform must take place in parallel with the overarching goals to build back better and reduce learning loss for students post-COVID. BBB activities can be aligned with factors impacting the curriculum implementation:

What to invest in?

What to invest in [to reach the poorest]?

Education Data

Collect appropriate,
usable data.
Get it used for
decision making.

Teacher professional development

Follow best evidence.
Don't fragment.
Share resources.

Radio, print, TV

Share resources.
Accessibility.
Open licensing,
editable.

What not to invest in [to reach the poorest]?

Online learning /
platforms /
e-content

Use radio, print, TV
instead.

Video lessons

Use Ubongo Kids /
Sesame St. / Digital
Storytime instead.

Internet /
broadband

Minimal connectivity
for WA/Telegram etc
is helpful. But *that's*
all folks...

SaveOurFuture — Ask 1. Collect and use the right education data

Strengthen education systems and workforce management with digital approaches to collect and analyse school- and learner-level data to better understand needs and address inequity.

- Develop context-specific and comparable data collection, data analysis and data storage protocols
- Collect data on educational infrastructure, enrollment and the number and geographic distribution of teachers and other members of the education workforce
- Act on this data to ensure resources are targeted to the most marginalised students, teachers, and schools
- Establish effective communication channels with and among the education workforce — education leadership, teachers, caregivers, learning teams — to coordinate education responses

Know thy...system.

SaveOurFuture — Ask 2. Enhance teacher and workforce development

Enhance the quality, reach, and flexibility of school-based professional development for teachers focusing on student learning, including a wide range of holistic skills, and drawing on appropriate and cost-effective technology.

- Promote effective means of professional development: regularly scheduled school-based professional development for school-centered learning teams (teachers, parents, community workers)
- Professional development needs to focus on effective teaching practices for improved, active student learning and to utilise technology for coordination and communication
- Act on school-level data (Ask 1) to ensure teacher education programs reach teachers in the most marginalised communities

Get every child a teacher.

SaveOurFuture — Ask 3. Promote inclusion and equity of learning outcomes

Ensure that every child can learn effectively — particularly those marginalised by poverty, gender, language, disability, or displacement — using appropriate learning and teaching resources, drawing on suitable technology where it offers value-for-money.

- National governments to use open curricular content and to ensure that there will be low- or no-cost ways for teachers, parents, and students to access content digitally, offline, through radio, through television, or in print
- Co-create mechanisms to share openly licensed, printable and editable content for the core curriculum including teacher guides, structured lesson plans, textbooks, workbooks, teacher professional development materials, and other multimodal resources in accessible, user-friendly formats and local languages, and targeted by learner level, for use inside and outside of the classroom

Get every child a book.

Thank you!

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<https://edtechhub.org>

<https://docs.edtechhub.org>

Further reading

Haßler, B., Nicolai, S., McBurnie, C., Jordan, K., Wilson, S., & Kreimeia, A. (2020). *EdTech and COVID-19 response [Save Our Future]* (Background Paper No. 3; #SaveOurFuture). Education Commission.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3983877>. Available from <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/SXDQAPB6>.

Forthcoming: Esbeck, C., Oloa, C., Brown, V., Plaut, D., & Salami, T. (2021). *Mango Tree Literacy Labs' Radio Programme Sandbox (Overview Report)* [Sprint Review]. EdTech Hub.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4747475>. Available from <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/RIPJWUDB>. Available under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

For more evidence, see: <https://docs.edtechhub.org>.

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